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THEME "DIGITAL ECONOMY - DIGITAL SOCIETY"

Ho Chi Minh City, November 2022

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FOSTERING GLOBAL CITIZENSHIP AMONG STUDENTS AND DEVELOPING THEIR DIGITAL SKILLS IN THE CONTEXT OF A DIGITAL SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT:

We are in the era of industry 4.0's digital revolution, where technology affects how individuals communicate, learn, and think. Especially for the students, the key value they wish to pursue in this digital society is to improve the digital competence and become global citizens. In this research, we first provide the definitions of global citizenship and digital transformation. The benefits for Vietnamese students are then discussed concerning how digital transformation affects their global citizen goal. By applying the latest digital competency framework, we suggest the skills should be equipped to improve students' digital literacy. Accordingly, governments and organizations should concentrate on the capacity to create and manage relationships and civilized conduct appropriate for digital citizens around the world. Therefore, students should be equipped and improve their (1) digital safety skills, (2) foreign language skills, (3) computer technology skills, (4) self-image on a digital platform, and (5) relationships and behavior. The findings of this study can be applied to improve the quality of students in this 4.0 era.

KEYWORDS: *digital transformation, digital society, digital citizenship, digital capacity.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation [1] is not only understood as the application of technological advances such as cloud computing and big data to all activities of organizations and businesses to achieve high efficiency, but also change. It is also a revolution in organizational thinking, bringing an overall and comprehensive change to individuals and organizations in their ways of living, working, and methods based on digital technology.

Global citizens [2] are people who live and work in numerous different nations and may be of more than one nationality. Additionally, this phrase refers to those who have a wide range of information, from the most fundamental to the customs and cultures of numerous nations around the world. Therefore, "global citizens" have the capacity to connect knowledge and growth possibilities in order to produce valuable contributions to the global society. They serve as a representation of human endeavors and improve the planet.

In the current digital transformation context, Vietnam is a pioneer in the national digital transformation plan. In 2020, the Prime Minister issued Decision No. 749/QĐ-TTg [3] approving the "National Digital Transformation Program to 2025" with a

vision and orientation to 2030, Vietnam becoming a digital, stable and prosperous country. Besides, Vietnam is a pioneer in applying new technologies and models. Renovating the operation, management, and administration of the Government through the fact that Vietnam has increased 2 places in the world ranking of e-Government.

Since the younger generation of Vietnamese people was born during a period of rapid technological advancement, they tend to be sensitive, easily adaptable, and open to embracing new technologies. The Vietnamese people also have a culture that is open to new ideas due to their spirit of integration and are open to accepting the progressive and positive values of the outside world.

The biggest obstacle to digital transformation is culture [4], because most individuals want to adopt new ideas as rapidly as possible without realizing that culture is the cornerstone of any thought revolution. More specifically, some people still operate in the same manner and with the same mindset because they are "afraid of change" and "the water comes to the feet to jump." In order to give Vietnamese youth many opportunities to access and learn many cutting-edge values and technologies, it is important to establish a culture of enhancing digital capacity among students. This will send a strong message to the next generation and lay the foundation for them to become global citizens in the digital age.

2. THE EFFORT TO INCREASE VIETNAMESE DIGITAL PROFICIENCY OF STUDENTS

2.1. Digital literacy definition and steps to digital literacy

Digital competence, according to Jan Secker [5], is the capacity to understand how to use digital tools for study and expression and to rationally examine and critically think about the vast amount of data that is available.

However, as defined by UNESCO [6], digital competence is the ability to safely and appropriately access, administer, understand, combine, communicate, evaluate and create information through digital technology to serve services for the unskilled labor market, senior jobs and business start-ups. Digital competence is also understood as computer skills, information technology capabilities, information or communication capabilities.

Vietnamese students need to develop their digital competencies in order to participate responsibly and actively in the present environment (how to utilize technology best, how to secure personal information on digital platforms). Build relationships and civilized behaviors on digital platforms, participate in communities at all levels, and increase empathy through online dialogues.

The government and organizations must establish a clear and suitable roadmap for Vietnamese students in order to enhance the application of digital culture and build and promote digital culture among Vietnamese students.

In order to create an evaluation framework and roadmap for digital competence and digital culture fit for Vietnamese students, the government and organizations should first survey the level of digital literacy among young people today.

Building and developing a framework for assessing digital competency is part of a strategic objective to improve people' fluency in digital languages and digital skills. However, based on the objectives and advancement of the nation and organization, distinct digital competency frameworks will be adopted and developed for various countries and audiences.

It is required to coordinate with relevant parties, ministries and departments sectors to bring out the proper digital competences in order to offer a framework for digital competency that is appropriate for Vietnamese students. To put it into practice, governments and organizations must set goals for activities for students in universities, colleges, and other educational levels in Vietnam in order to provide a measure and appropriate assessment through the successful implementation of the aforementioned competency frameworks.

2.2. Some capacity frameworks in the world

2.2.1. Europe Digital Competency Framework [7]

In 2017, with the support of the European Commission, the JRC studied a strategy to promote digital capabilities for Europe. The "DigComp 2.0" project is considered as a tool to promote digital capacity for citizens with 5 competency criteria:

1. Information and data processing capacity through browsing, searching, browsing data, information and digital content; evaluate and manage data, information and digital content.
2. Proficient in information and data through interaction through digital information technology; sharing through digital technologies; participation in citizenship through digital technology; cooperation through digital technology; understanding and observing social etiquette; manage.
3. Content creation through digital content development; integrate and rebuild digital content; copyrights and licenses; program.
4. Safety through device protection; protection of personal data and privacy; protect health and well-being; environmental protection.
5. Problem solving through technical problem solving; identifying technology needs and responses; creative use of digital technologies; digital identity.

2.2.2. UNESCO Digital Competency Framework [8]

In 2018, based on the European Five Forces Digital Framework, UNESCO conducted a proposal for a global digital competency framework, of which UNESCO proposed two more areas:

1. Ability to operate digital devices through understanding the operation of hardware and software devices.
2. Career-oriented competencies related through operating specific digital technologies in a particular field and interpreting and manipulating data and digital content for a particular field.

2.3. Proposing improvements to the digital competency framework:

The existing competency frameworks of countries and organizations around the world are generally classified and arranged in a downward direction that emphasizes technical factors in operations and focuses on applying technology to practice through attitude, empathy, critical thinking and problem solving, innovation. However, the above digital competency frameworks do not address the psychological capacity of students.

In the digital age, social networks have become a communication and entertainment tool for young people and are used on a regular basis. Social networking platforms are developed and improved continuously for the purpose of stimulating users to use more time. Therefore, the influence of social networks on human psychology will become more profound over time. Specifically, here are some of the negative effects of social media on psychology.

Online bullying [9] is a type of bullying that takes place on computers, smartphones, laptops, and other electronic devices. Direct bullies may criticize, critique, or make threatening remarks to their victims. Many people tell jokes that are hurtful and extremely upsetting to others since they are not face-to-face. Students and youngsters are typically the victims in this predicament. False information can be widely disseminated on social media platforms if prompt handling procedures are not taken, subjecting victims to intense emotional stress.

FOMO (fear of missing out) [10] is a psychological problem that has only recently emerged. This syndrome is mainly seen in young people with the characteristic that they are always worried about falling behind and being inferior to others in an exaggerated and extreme way. There are many causes of FOMO syndrome, of which frequent social media use is the most common. FOMO syndrome also makes each person lose their own opinions and all decisions are dependent on the majority trend.

To protect their own psychology, students need to understand digital skills through understanding social networks and real life and seek help from experts. In addition, as social networks facilitate the connection of all friends worldwide, students must be able to establish and maintain relationships on these platforms. This gives pupils more opportunities for study and growth as well as exposure to different cultures and aspects of life. But it's important to take the right precautions to avoid fraud and spot dishonest actors on social media.

As a result, in order to improve the quality of the evaluation framework for digital competency, it is necessary to be more aware of social networks and one's own interests as well as to be able to create and maintain relationships on social media.

3. KNOWLEDGE AND ABILITIES THAT RESIDENTS OF THE WORLD REQUIRE IN THE DIGITAL AGE

By applying the latest digital competency framework, we suggest the skills should be equipped to improve students' digital literacy.

3.1. Digital safety skills

Equip skills in dealing with behavioral risks in cyberspace by learning how to deal with cyberbullying, harassment and stalking on digital platforms, and identifying and dealing with cyberbullying. Respond to cyber content risks by understanding harmful user-generated content such as racist, hateful, discriminatory, or abusive content and images. photos, to strengthen themselves, to actively contribute to a healthy online community. At the same time, protect yourself with personal security management practices by being aware and alert to thefts of confidential information and personal data, and how to use secure security measures. Using safe passwords and anti-virus software, learning how to deal with when personal information is exposed online, Facebook account security, and using social networks not to reveal personal data are also necessary skills a user should be equipped with.

3.2. Foreign language skills

Foreign languages are a prerequisite to becoming a global citizen in the digital age, because young people will not be able to work with foreign partners and companies with their mother tongue. Having a background of knowledge of foreign languages makes it easy for students to handle situations arising in different countries. Foreign languages are also the key to help students access vast sources of knowledge, expand relationships through communication in foreign languages, and the process of learning and acquiring different languages also helps students develop. the brain's memory capacity and capacity development in this digital age.

3.3. Computer technology skills

As the globe transitions to the 4.0 technology era, students can now readily access information technology, acquire computer technology fundamentals, and obtain knowledge using laptops. and mobile devices. To be a digital citizen, students must master a certain level of technology use, including the use of laptops, smartphones, and other electronic devices, as well as the ability to access and deeply understand the internet by mastering the skills of online information searching, useful knowledge acquisition, information filtering, and the search for reliable information sources. Understand how to use applications, services, and shopping to meet individual needs.

3.4. Building a self-image on a digital platform

Enhance the social media presence by creating a virtual identity online, creating a personal profile on Facebook, actively matching your interests with posts, sharing meaningful content, understanding the difference between reality and virtuality when using social media, and actively disseminating upbeat and encouraging information to create a positive self-image.

3.5. Skills to build, manage relationships and behavior in a civilized manner suitable for global digital citizens

Building and managing relationships on digital platforms is a matter of little concern in Vietnam. Students need to develop skills through learning the rules about using social networks so as not to hurt others, how to protect themselves psychologically so as not to be affected by social networks. In addition, students need to learn how to recognize people, do good and bad actions on digital platforms, and build and maintain relationships on social networks. At the same time, students need to know how to deal with dangers on social networks. From there, creating a meaningful global citizen.

4. CONCLUSION

In the current industry 4.0, digital transformation and global digital citizenship are of great interest to society. Today's young people in Vietnam were born in a period of great change in technology, this trend creates young people who are sensitive and easily adaptable, ready to adapt and approach new technologies. However, the biggest barrier in digital transformation is culture when most people want to quickly follow new trends but forget that culture is the foundation of any thinking revolution. Therefore, in order to improve the application of digital culture, build and promote digital culture among Vietnamese students, the government and organizations need to have a specific and appropriate roadmap for Vietnamese students through the framework. Digital competence is supplemented with the ability to be aware of social networks and one's own interests as well as the ability to build and manage relationships on social networks.

In addition, the young Vietnamese generation has to develop social skills, learn more foreign languages, and acquire digital safety knowledge so that they can participate in the process of becoming global citizens in the digital age. with the ability to establish oneself on a digital platform, manage connections, and act in a manner that is appropriate for global digital citizens. prepared with technology skills for the 4.0 era.

With these values, the young Vietnamese generation is ready to become global citizens in the digital society. From there, surely the goal of a prosperous Vietnam in 2045 will be brilliantly successful.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ebert, Christof, and Carlos Henrique C. Duarte. "Digital transformation." *IEEE Softw.* 35.4 (2018): 16-21.
- [2] Dower, Nigel, and John Williams. *Global citizenship: A critical introduction.* Routledge, 2016.

- [3] Minister, Prime, and Decision No. "749/QD-TTg dated June 3, 2020 of the Prime Minister approving the National Digital Transformation Program to 2025, with a Vision to 2030." (2020).
- [4] Çetin Gürkan, Güney, and Gülsel Çiftci. "Developing a supportive culture in digital transformation." *Digital Business Strategies in Blockchain Ecosystems*. Springer, Cham, 2020. 83-102.
- [5] Secker, Jane. "The trouble with terminology: rehabilitating and rethinking 'Digital Literacy'." (2017): 3-16.
- [6] Fernández-Batanero, José María, et al. "Digital competences for teacher professional development. Systematic review." *European Journal of Teacher Education* (2020): 1-19.
- [7] Carretero, Stephanie, Riina Vuorikari, and Yves Punie. "The digital competence framework for citizens." Publications Office of the European Union (2017).
- [8] Law, Nancy, David Woo, and Gary Wong. *A global framework of reference on digital literacy skills for indicator 4.4. 2*. No. 51. UNESCO, 2018.
- [9] Freis, Stephanie D., and Regan AR Gurung. "A Facebook analysis of helping behavior in online bullying." *Psychology of popular media culture* 2.1 (2013): 11.
- [10] Milyavskaya, Marina, et al. "Fear of missing out: prevalence, dynamics, and consequences of experiencing FOMO." *Motivation and Emotion* 42.5 (2018): 725-737.